

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

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D3.4 Molecular markers for whitefly resistance

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

IPM	Integrated Pest Management
QTL	Quantitative Trait Locus
RIL	Recombinant Inbred Line
F6	Filial Generation 6
AP2/ERF	APETALA2/ethylene response factor
TAR1	Trichome and Artemisinin Regulator 1
kb	Kilobase
LOD	Logarithm of Odds
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
UTR	Untranslated Region
qPCR	quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction
SEM	Standard Error of the Mean
HSD	Honestly Significant Difference
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
CRISPR-Cas	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats–CRISPR Associated

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Whiteflies cause major damage in tomato cultivation, mainly through transmission of viruses that cause disease. To control whiteflies, insecticides are widely used, but the overuse of insecticides can result in resistance development in pest insects and is harmful to humans and the environment. As an alternative strategy, the use of plants with resistance against whiteflies is an effective solution that fits in an integrated pest management (IPM) approach. Here, we used a wild relative of tomato, *S. galapagense*, that was previously found to have broad spectrum insect resistance associated with the presence of glandular trichomes. Glandular trichomes, which are hair-like structures on the leaves with secretory glands, produce secondary metabolites that can be toxic, deter oviposition and trap insects. Type IV trichomes are known to produce acyl sugars that can stick and kill whiteflies. Previously, the whitefly resistance in *S. galapagense* was mapped to a major QTL, Wf-1, at the end of chromosome 2. Within task 3.2, we performed fine-mapping on QTL Wf-1 to decrease the genomic region for whitefly resistance and generate markers linked to trichome type IV presence and whitefly resistance. A recombinant inbred line (RIL) population was generated from a cross between *S. galapagense* and *S. lycopersicum*. From this RIL population, a single F6 plant, that was heterozygous for the region on chromosome 2, was selfed to generate a mapping population. First, 1152 heterozygous plants were genotyped with 2 markers that flanked the 2-LOD interval of 410 kb that was previously identified. The use of these markers led to the identification of 56 recombinants. To further fine-map the region for the whitefly resistance, we designed and analyzed additional markers on the recombinants. Heterozygous plants were phenotyped for the presence of type IV trichomes, which resulted in a 13kb region for type IV trichomes presence and whitefly resistance. The markers that were used to fine-map both traits are provided. Finally, we discuss a potential candidate gene present in the 13kb genomic region.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Whitefly issues in tomato

Two whitefly species cause major problems in cultivated tomato in Europe: the greenhouse whitefly (*Trialeurodes vaporariorum*) and the sweet potato whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci* species complex). Whiteflies damage plants by feeding on the phloem, causing direct damages such as wilting and reducing growth. However, the main impact of whiteflies on tomato is due to their role as virus vector. In particular, *B. tabaci* can transmit over 100 pathogenic viruses, including important viruses such as those in the group of Tomato yellow leaf curl virus.

To control whiteflies, the use of insecticides is still the main strategy. However, the overuse of insecticides often results in resistance development and is harmful to humans and the environment. Integrated pest management (IPM) approaches, which involve selective pesticides, and biological, physical, and cultural controls are also used to suppress whiteflies. The use of host plant resistance is an effective solution that fits in an IPM approach (Broekgaarden et al., 2011).

2.2 Resistance to whiteflies in tomato

As effective levels of resistance to whitefly are not present in cultivated tomato, wild relatives have been screened to identify resistances against this pest. Several wild relatives of tomato were found to have increased insect resistance including *Solanum pennellii*, *S. pimpinellifolium*, *S. galapagense* and *S. habrochaites* (Mirnezhad et al., 2010; Firdaus et al., 2012; McDaniel et al., 2016; Rakha et al., 2017; Vosman et al., 2018; Kortbeek et al., 2021). In several of these species, resistance against insects has been associated with the presence of glandular type IV trichomes.

Trichomes are epidermal hair-like structures on the leaves (Glas et al., 2012; Schuurink & Tissier, 2020). Different types of trichomes exist and they can be classified based on their structure, and absence or presence of glands (glandular vs. non-glandular trichomes). In plants in the genus *Solanum*, trichomes type II, III, V & VIII are non-glandular, whilst trichomes type I, IV, VI & VII are glandular (Figure 1). In defense against insects, non-glandular trichomes can have a role as physical barriers that obstruct insect movement and feeding. Glandular trichomes additionally produce secondary metabolites that can be antifeedant (toxic), deter oviposition, trap insects and recruit natural enemies (Glas et al., 2012; Schuurink & Tissier, 2020). Type IV trichomes are particularly known to produce acyl sugars. Acyl sugars deter insect attacks by sticking and positing insects to the leaves. Cultivated tomato, *S. lycopersicum*, has no glandular trichomes in mature leaves, while some wild relatives, including *S. galapagense*, have many of these type IV trichomes (Glas et al., 2012; Vendemiatti et al., 2017), Figure 1).

Figure 1. *Trichome types present in wild and cultivated Solanum accessions.* A) Type I, IV, VI and VII are glandular trichomes, and Type II, III, V and VIII are non-glandular trichomes. B) Representation of trichomes present in cultivated variety MoneyMaker: Type II, V, VI and VII. C) Representation of trichomes present in *Solanum galapagense*: Type I, IV, VI and VII. Figures modified from Vendemiatti et al. (2022).

For Virtigation task 3.2, we used an accession of *Solanum galapagense* that was previously shown to have broad spectrum resistance against two whitefly species (*T. vaporariorum* and *B. tabaci*), the thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis*, caterpillar *Spodoptera exigua* and aphid *Myzus persicae* (Vosman et al., 2018). Resistance to whiteflies was mapped to a major QTL (called Wf-1) on the end of chromosome 2 by using an F2 population that was derived from a cross between *MoneyMaker*^{tmvR} PRI91117 and *S. galapagense* PRI95004. The presence of this QTL from *Solanum galapagense* also corresponded to the presence of trichome type IV and reduced performance of *B. tabaci* (Firdaus et al., 2013). In addition, resistance to another whitefly species, *Trialeurodes vaporariorum*, was also mapped in a RIL population that was derived from this F2 population (Vosman et al., 2019). Finally, QTLs for resistance to both whitefly species, trichome type IV development, and more than 200 non-volatile metabolites, including 76 acyl sugars, were shown to all co-locate at the end of chromosome 2 of *Solanum galapagense* (Vosman et al., 2019). It is thus expected that Wf-1 is regulating the formation of glandular trichome type IV on the leaf epidermis, enabling the production and accumulation of bioactive metabolites in this type of trichomes, that leads to resistance to whiteflies.

Here, we perform fine-mapping on Wf-1 to decrease the genomic region that leads to whitefly resistance and provide markers linked to trichome type IV development and whitefly resistance. In the genetic region, a potential candidate gene is identified.

3 FINEMAPPING OF QTL & MARKERS

The Wf1 QTL on chromosome 2 is important for resistance to whiteflies *B. tabaci* and *T. vaporariorum* and, for trichome type IV production, and is a hotspot for metabolite production especially of acyl sugars. Here, we performed fine-mapping to identify a smaller genetic region that is linked to trichome development and whitefly resistance.

3.1 Fine-mapping of QTL Wf-1

An F6 plant of a RIL population derived from a cross between *S. galapagense* LA1401 (PRI95004) and *S. lycopersicum* MoneyMaker^{tmvR} (PRI91117) was used, and selfed. First, 1152 heterozygous plants were genotyped with 2 markers, flanking the 2-LOD interval of 410 kb that was identified before (Vosman et al., 2019). Using these markers, 56 recombinants were identified (4.9%). Additional markers were then designed on the recombinants to fine-map the trait. All lines were phenotyped for presence of type IV trichomes. We found that presence of only type IV trichomes led to high whitefly survival, while plants with 50:50 type VI:type V had intermediate resistance. As can be seen in figure 2, in genotypes with only the *S. galapagense* allele, all trichomes that were present were of type IV, while genotypes with the MoneyMaker allele only had type V trichomes. Using these markers, the region that leads to production of type IV trichomes and whitefly resistance was mapped to a 13kb region (SL4.0) (Figure 2).

101 = *S. galapagense*
102 = heterozygote
202 = *S. lycopersicum*

Marker	67551	SNP11	C	D	E	F	F_1	N	G	H	I	20052	Trichome type	
	51867839	52082019	52104437	52109141	52109522	52112715	52120830	52131740	52133936	52135196	52156770	52162665	IV	V
SL4.0														
R174A	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	100	0
O2A12	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	102	102	100	0
O2C08	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	102	102	102	102	100	0
O8C06	101	101	101	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	50	50
12C08	101	202	202	202	202	202	202	102	102	102	102	102	50	50
12B11	101	202	202	202	202	202	102	102	102	102	102	102	50	50
O8A05	101	202	202	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	50	50
O9A03	101	202	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	50	50
O5F05	101	102	102	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	0	100
O1D04	101	102	102	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	0	100
O9D07	101	102	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	0	100
R174B	101	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	0	100

13 kb region

Figure 2. Result of the fine-mapping of the Wf-1 QTL. Twelve plants were genotyped with the markers in the top row and have either the *S. galapagense* allele (101, red), *S. lycopersicum* allele (202, green) or were heterozygous (102, blue). Lines were phenotyped for percentage of presence of trichomes, focusing on type IV and type V, and showed either only type IV, only type V, or a 50:50 distribution. The 13 kb region important for presence of type IV trichomes is indicated. The sequences of the markers are provided in Table 1. The positions of the markers on the SL4.0 genome is indicated.

3.2 Markers for whitefly resistance

Twelve markers were used to genotype plants segregating for whitefly resistance and presence of trichome type IV. The sequences of SNPs can be found in Table 1. The top marker associated with presence of trichomes type IV is marker N.

Marker	SL4.0	Sequence and SNP [X/Y]
67551	51867839	GCATACACTATTCTTGGAAATTGTCTACAACCTTTTCCCTCATTTTCTCT[T/C]ACTTGATCTTACTGTAACATCAAAAATTCCTTAATGGAAGCTGCC
SNP11	52082019	GCTAGTTGACCTTGCTAGTATATGTAGCTTGACATCACCAGAACAGAGACCAACAATGAGGCAAATCTTAAAAA[G/A]ATACAAGATATAAAGGATAGTGCAA TGGTCGAGAATAACAAAA
C	52104437	ACTGGAGTATCCTTCCATCAATTCTTTGGTTTCCATGAACCTAACCCCTTTATTT[T/C]TCTTTGGTCTTTCTGCTTTTGCAATTATCATTTTCTTGACGACATATAT AGATATGCAAAATCACGGATGGGATTGCGTAGTAAGAAATCAAGGTAAAT
D	52109141	CATTCACCTCCAGCTTTTGCCTTTTCATGGGTTTCTTCTCTCTCTCCAGTTAGCTCTAGATTACAGGGAAACAAAATTTTGTAAATTCAGTCCCTGTAATTTCA CATAAATAATTATATACA[G/A]TCAAAGATGGAGATAGGTGGTGGGGTCAAAGTGGAGTTGCTGCAAAATTCAGGGGTTTGTGTGGTGGGAAGAGAAAAGAA CGAAAAGCCCTA
E	52109522	CCGAGTTGTTAGTTGGTGATGGTGGCTTAATGATTGTCTGCTGCTTGCATTGCTGTAAGAAAAGCCATAGAAGTTGGTGCTCAAGTAGATGCTGTACAGAACTCG CTTGCAACCCATCATA[A/G]CCATACAGAGAAAAGGTGCACCTGAGACGGCAAGCCCTCAGAATTGAAGCCTTGTGGTTCAAGAGAAGCCGATTTAAA CTTGAAGCCCGAGCCCGAAGA
F	52112715	TCAAACCTCGAAAAGTTGACTCGAAAACCTTTGCTTTTGAACAGTATTATCTATTAGAATGAACCTGCAATGCTCTAAAAGGCCAAGTTTCACTATTCTCTAC[A /T]AGATTGCTAATTTACATGAATATATCCTAGCTGACACAGTATGCTGAGAAGTGCAGTTTATAAAATTAAGCTGACTGCCTTGACCACAGATCCTGTGGAA GAAGGGACAACTGTGTTACTGTTTTTAAAC
F_1	52120830	TTATTTTTTAAACTGACTAAAAATAAAGTATGTCCGGAGAAAATACGGATAGAAAACCTCATAACTTTTCAAAGTGCAAAATGAGTAAAAGTATAATTT[G/A] CTTTTCTTAGGAAAATATGTTCAAAGTTAAAAACCAAGCGAAAACCTTTTATGAACTACCAAAGCCAAAAGGAAAATGGAGCCAGGGAAAAGCATATG
N	52131740	AAAAAACCTAAATTTTCAATGTTGTAC[G/C]GACGTGAGATATGTGAACAGAAAATAATAGGAGAAAATAGCCGCAGAAAAGTGGCGTTACGAGGATCCGTAAA GTCGGTGTAGAGA
G	52133936	GAGAGGTAAAATTTCCGGCTTCTCTATGGTGGGTCTGGGTAACGGCGATGAAGAACAGCCGGTGACCCGACAGTTTTTTCCGGTTGATGAGTCGGAAATGGGT GGTGTGCTGCTGAAAATGGAT[G/C]CCCGAATTTCCAGAGCTCACTGGGTTGGAGTTAAATTTACCAAACGGAGACACTGGCAACACGGGATTGGCCAG GCCTGTAGATATGGTTACAGCAGCAACAGCAGCCTAT
H	52135197	AGATTGAAGCTGCCAGGTGTGGTTGGCCGAATTTATCTCTACTACTTAACCTCAATTACTTTTGAATTAAGTAAATTTAAGGTAGTTATTTCTTTTGT AATACAGAGC[G/T]TATGATAAAGCTGCCATCAAGTGAACGGGAAGGATGCA
I	52156770	ACTTCTTCAACCCACACAAGAAGCGTGTAGTGGTTAACAGTTGACACACTCACCTCTCTCCCTACGCTCCG[T/C]CAACCCAAAGCAACCCGCAAACTTT TTCTCTCTGCTCCTCTCAC
20052	52162665	GATGAACGGCGTCAAAAACCTTTCTTTGGGGTGTGATGGTATCACTAGT[T/G]GTTTCTGAAGTTGTAGATATCACCTTATCAAAGAGAAGCTGCATCCCCAGG

Table 1. Markers used to fine-map whitefly resistance and presence of trichomes type IV in a RIL population derived from *S. galapagense* LA1401 (PRI95004) and *S. lycopersicum* *MoneyMaker*^{tmvR} (PRI91117).

4 QTL REGION AND CANDIDATE GENE

Fine-mapping led to a region of 13kb. In this chapter, this region is examined.

4.1 QTL region

The region that was found to contribute to whitefly resistance is between marker F_1 and G. In the *S. lycopersicum* SL4.0 genome, this corresponds to a region of 13 kb, which starts just after gene Solyc02g093140, and ends in the next gene, Solyc093150.

4.1.1 Candidate gene

The top marker (F_1, Table 1) localizes in the 5' UTR of Solyc02g093150. This gene encodes for transcription factor APETALA2c (AP2c), and is part of the APETALA2/ethylene response factor (AP2/ERF) transcription factors family, characterized by conserved AP2/ERF DNA binding domains. Members of AP2/ERF transcription factors function as key regulators in plant metabolism, development, and adaptive responses to environmental stimuli.

In *Artemisia annua*, an AP2/ERF transcription factor, TAR1, is involved in the development of trichomes and the biosynthesis of artemisinin (Tan et al., 2015). This gene is thus a good candidate for development of glandular trichomes in *Solanum*.

To study the potential involvement of AP2c in trichome formation, we studied AP2c expression in *S. lycopersicum* MM, *S. galapagense* LA1401, and a RIL line that contains either the AP2c sequence from *S. lycopersicum* (R174A) or that from *S. lycopersicum* (R174B). First, we confirmed the differences in trichome type IV count in the different genotypes (Figure 3a and b). Microscopy pictures were taken from the adaxial and abaxial side of each leaf from 9-week old plants, using the Keyence VHX-7000 microscope with a 200x magnification (Figure 3A). The program Fiji ImageJ 1.53 was used to make selection areas and manually count glandular trichome in in four equal sized selection areas on both abaxial and adaxial leaf surfaces. Type IV trichomes were only found in *S. galapagense* LA1401 and in R174A, and density was higher in abaxial side then on the adaxial side (Figure 3B).

Next, we performed qPCR analysis to determine the transcript levels of AP2c in both leaf and trichome tissue. Pooled trichomes were collected from fresh leaf material from all plants. For that, a frozen paint brush was used to harvest trichomes in liquid nitrogen after which trichomes passed a 120 μm sieve (VWR) (Balcke et al., 2014). The reference gene *EF1 α* was used to calculate relative expression of AP2c. The transcript levels of AP2c were low and was not significantly different in the leaf samples between the four genotypes. Transcript levels of AP2c were increased in trichomes from plant genotypes with high levels of type IV trichomes when compared to the leaves, especially in plant material from R174A.

Figure 3 A) Pictures of trichomes observed on leaves (adaxial side) from four genotypes. Coloured arrows are used to indicate glandular trichome types where yellow: Type I, red: Type IV, blue: Type VI and pink: Type VII. B) Average counts of type IV trichomes on abaxial and adaxial side of leaves of four genotypes. Averages were taken from three leaf surface observations, error bars represent the SEM. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in average trichome counts between

pairwise genotype combinations. An asterisk indicates a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in trichome count between the abaxial and adaxial leaf surface. **C)** Relative gene expression of *AP2c* of pooled leaf and trichome samples ($n=10$). The average was taken from three harvest moments, each harvesting moment consisted of four technical replicates were used in qPCR. A One-Way ANOVA analysis, followed by Tukey's HSD test revealed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in fold change expression between pairwise genotype combinations. These are indicated with different letters, respectively capital and small letters for leaf and trichome material. Error bars represent the SEM.

ANNEX 1: REFERENCES

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